

CUSTOMER PERCEPTION TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING WEBSITE

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Abstract:

Online shopping is defined as the process a customer takes to purchase a service or product over the internet. In other words, a consumer may at his or her leisure buy from the comfort of their own home products from an online store. The main objective is to study the consumer's expectation towards online shopping and to study about the customer's opinion towards the problems in online shopping. For this a sample of 81 was collected from the respondents were percentage analysis, chi-square analysis and one way Anova were used as tools to analyse the data and the conclusion is that The frequency of shopping online by the customers was made during heavy discount period and the companies can try to increase the frequency of providing more discounts so that the volume of trade can be increased and it leads to increase in customer base for the companies. The companies need to keep everything on your site up to date. If they have a blog it needs to be updated regularly, they should feature new and popular products and replace them when they have new items to discover.

Key Words: Online Shopping, Expectation & Popular Products

Introduction:

Online shopping is the process whereby consumers directly buy goods or services from a seller in real-time, without an intermediary service, over the Internet. It is a form of electronic commerce. An online shop, e-shop, e-store, Internet shop, web shop, web store, online store, or virtual store evokes the physical analogy of buying products or services at a bricks-and-mortar retailer or in a shopping center. The process is called business-to-consumer (B2C) online shopping. When a business buys from another business, it is called business-to-business (B2B) online shopping. The study is about analysing the customer perception towards online shopping at local online shopping website. It is a marketing concept that encompasses a customer's impression, awareness and/or consciousness about a company or its offerings. Customer perception is typically affected by advertising, reviews, public relations, social media, personal experiences and other channels.

Objectives:

- ✓ To study the consumer's expectation towards online shopping.
- ✓ To compare the customer preference to purchase online and dimensions related to online shopping
- ✓ To know the perception of customers towards online shopping.
- ✓ To suggest the companies about perception of customers towards online shopping

Scope of the Study:

E-commerce creates new opportunities for entrepreneurial start-ups. Ease of Internet access, Safe and secure payment modes coupled with aggressive marketing by E-Commerce Giants has revolutionized this segment. Rapid development in mobile technology has given way to Mobile Commerce with many E-Commerce companies shifting to App only model. The main scope of the study is that it will be helpful for the companies to maintain their quality of service based on customers in future period of time.

Review of Literature:

Weber, K. and Roehl, W. S. (1999)¹, conducted a study on those who search for or purchase travel products through on-line with the age group of 26 to 55 years. Results on the basis of the study concerns about credit card security, evaluation of product quality, and privacy issues are the main problems faced while on-line purchase of travel products, were made.

Vellido et al. (2000)², pointed out in his research, that there are nine factors associated with user's perception of online shopping. Among those factors the risk perception of users was demonstrated to be the main discriminator between people buying online and people not buying online. Other discriminating factors were control over, and convenience of, the shopping process, affordability of merchandise, customer service and ease of use of the shopping site.

Research Methodology:

Reliability and Validity:

Area of the Study: The survey was conducted with customers who shop online in Coimbatore City.

Sampling Design: As the study is based on customers the samples don't have criteria and for this purpose convenience sampling is used for the research.

Data Sources: The study used both primary data and secondary data.

The primary data was collected through field survey in the study area. First-hand information's pertaining to the benefits derived and the various competencies encountered were collected from 30 customers to know about activities towards project management.

Tools Used for Collection of Data: Frequency analysis, ANOVA and Descriptive statistics.

Analysis and Interpretation:

		Frequency	Percent
Preference to Purchase online	Yes	53	65.4
	No	28	34.6
	Total	81	100.0
Willing to access the online Grocery within their premise	Online Grocery Retailer	44	54.3
	Supermarket Store	37	45.7
	Total	81	100.0

Out 81 respondents 65.4% said they purchase online, 34.6% said they won't purchase online. It shows that most of the respondents have preference to purchase online. 54.3% said they are willing to access online grocery retailer and 45.7% said they are willing to access super market store. It shows that most of the respondents are willing to access the online grocery within their premise.

Willing to Have Access Towards Various Aspects:

		Frequency	Percent
Willing to have access towards groceries	Online	34	42
	Super Market	47	58
	Total	81	100
Willing to have access towards organic farm products	Online	33	40.7
	Super Market	48	59.3
	Total	81	100
Willing to have access towards dairy Products	Online	29	35.8
	Super Market	52	64.2
	Total	81	100
Willing to have access towards Beverages	Online	37	45.7
	Super Market	44	54.3
	Total	81	100
Willing to have access towards Fruits & Vegetables	Online	28	34.6
	Super Market	53	65.4
	Total	81	100
Willing to have access towards Household	Online	46	56.8
	Super Market	35	43.2
	Total	81	100
Willing to have access towards health and personal care	Online	47	58
	Super Market	34	42
	Total	81	100
Willing to have access towards spices & masala	Online	43	53.1
	Super Market	38	46.9
	Total	81	100
Willing to have access towards Snacks	Online	36	45.6
	Super Market	44	54.3
	Total	81	100
Willing to have access towards Staples pulses & seed, grains	Online	35	43.2
	Super Market	46	56.8
	Total	81	100
Willing to have access towards baby care	Online	45	55.6
	Super Market	36	44.4
	Total	81	100
Willing to have access towards dry fruits	Online	41	50.6
	Super Market	40	49.4
	Total	81	100
Willing to have access towards frozen products	Online	29	35.8
	Super Market	52	64.2

	Total	81	100
Willing to have access towards ice cream	Online	23	29.6
	Super Market	57	70.4
	Total	81	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows about willing to have access towards groceries were out 81 respondents 42% have willing to have access towards groceries through online and 58% have willing to have access towards groceries through super market. It shows that most of the respondents are willing to have access towards groceries through super market. Most of the respondents have access towards organic farm products through super market. Most of the respondents have access towards dairy products through super market. Most of the respondents have access towards beverages, snacks, staples pulses & seed, grains and fruits, frozen products, ice cream & vegetables with super market. Most of the respondents have access towards household, health, baby care, dry fruits and personal care, spices & masala with online.

One Way Anova:

Comparison Between Preference to Purchase Online and Dimensions Related to Online Shopping Descriptives:

H0: There is no significant relationship between preference to purchase online and dimensions related to online shopping

H1: There is a significant relationship between preference to purchase online and dimensions related to online shopping

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig
Facing problems while purchasing online	Yes	53	3.1226	.78235	.052	.821
	No	28	3.1607	.57015		
	Total	81	3.1358	.71266		
Perception towards privacy with reference to online grocery shopping	Yes	53	3.9681	.70192	11.875	.001
	No	28	3.3693	.81845		
	Total	81	3.7611	.79275		
Perception towards security with reference to online grocery shopping	Yes	53	4.1192	.55462	7.797	.007
	No	28	3.6914	.81606		
	Total	81	3.9714	.68310		
Perception towards time saving with reference to online grocery shopping	Yes	53	3.6151	.80715	1.447	.233
	No	28	3.3950	.73469		
	Total	81	3.5390	.78532		
Perception towards convenience with reference to online grocery shopping	Yes	53	3.7530	.82161	3.230	.076
	No	28	3.4107	.80281		
	Total	81	3.6347	.82652		
Perception towards price with reference to online grocery shopping	Yes	53	3.8523	.64364	.971	.328
	No	28	3.6964	.73710		
	Total	81	3.7984	.67691		
Experience and expectation with online shopping based on culture	Yes	53	3.7547	.64018	.512	.476
	No	28	3.6400	.76697		
	Total	81	3.7151	.68406		
Experience and expectation with online shopping based on product	Yes	53	3.9423	.71751	4.089	.047
	No	28	3.6075	.69115		
	Total	81	3.8265	.72216		
Experience and expectation with online shopping based on promotion	Yes	53	3.7706	.62550	7.522	.008
	No	28	3.3346	.77502		
	Total	81	3.6199	.70750		
Experience and expectation with online shopping based on delivery	Yes	53	3.9340	.71413	5.417	.023
	No	28	3.5179	.85507		

	Total	81	3.7901	.78607		
Preference to shop online for various reasons	Yes	53	2.4608	.29626	.765	.384
	No	28	2.3971	.33839		
	Total	81	2.4388	.31085		

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the relationship between preference to purchase online and dimensions related to online shopping. It depicts that majority of the people don't face problems while purchasing online, the respondents who have perception towards privacy, time saving, convenience, price with reference to online grocery shopping, experience and expectation with online shopping based on culture, experience and expectation with online shopping based on product, experience and expectation with online shopping based on promotion and preference to shop online for various reasons have preference to purchase online.

Chi Square Analysis:

Willing to Access the Online Grocery Within their Premise * Facing Problems While Purchasing Online:

H0: There is no significant relationship between willing to access the online grocery within their premise and facing problems while purchasing online

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	9.268 ^a	13	.752

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the relationship between willing to access the online grocery within their premise and facing problems while purchasing online were the level of significance is at 0.752 which is greater than 0.05. It reveals that there is no significant relationship between willing to access the online grocery within their premise and facing problems while purchasing online.

Findings:

- ✓ Most of the respondents have preference to purchase online.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are willing to access the online grocery within their premise.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are willing to have access towards groceries through super market. Maximum of the respondents have access towards organic farm products through super market.
- ✓ Most of the respondents have access towards dairy products through super market and Most of the respondents have access towards beverages, snacks, staples pulses & seed, grains and fruits, frozen products, ice cream & vegetables with super market.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents have access towards household, health, baby care, dry fruits and personal care, spices & masala with online.
- ✓ Most of the respondents spend more than Rs.2000 per month.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are purchasing more than 5 times.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are purchasing more than 5 times.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are willing to pay below Rs 750 Delivery fee Rs 30 will be apply.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are buying for 30 minutes.

Suggestions:

The companies related to online shopping can promote their brand and products related with them more with male persons who are unmarried as they are using they are using the websites more when compared to other persons based on the study. More advertisements can be given through social media as most of the persons who are working in private organisations use the company's website to purchase a lot.

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that the companies need to keep everything on your site up to date. If they have a blog it needs to be updated regularly, they should feature new and popular products and replace them when they have new items to discover.

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